

Urgency and the shameful escape of privilege: We move differently when we refuse to set aside the weight: A response to Aldo Parra

David M. Bowers, University of Tennessee Knoxville, ✉ dbower14@utk.edu

In his plenary paper, Parra adopts a tone that is simultaneously kindly and urgent, at once friendly and keenly critical, as he surfaces deeply visceral aspects of the world as it exists today and the untapped power Mathematics Education has to respond to seemingly omnipresent violences. His observations and urgency culminate in a call to action: That we should not let the world define Mathematics Education, but instead embrace our communal power to define it ourselves in ways that defy the white supremacist, cis-hetero patriarchal, abled, parochial, neoliberal, late Capitalist systems that currently confine us. Here, I aim to expand on and amplify what I perceive as the essence of Parra's message, with particular focus on unsettling anticipated neoliberal critiques/evasions of Parra's call to action.

The white conservatives aren't friends of the Negro either, but they at least don't try to hide it. They are like wolves; they show their teeth in a snarl that keeps the Negro always aware of where he stands with them. But the white liberals are foxes, who also show their teeth to the Negro but pretend that they are smiling. The white liberals are more dangerous than the conservatives; they lure the Negro, and as the Negro runs from the growling wolf, he flees into the open jaws of the "smiling" fox. One is the wolf, the other is a fox. No matter what, they'll both eat you. (Malcolm X)

In his plenary address and manuscript, Parra (2021, in this volume) makes a series of thoughtful and keenly incisive observations regarding the state of the world as it exists today as well as regarding the often untapped power of communal/community organizing, culminating in a simple but extremely powerful call to action: "Then, we should not wait for [mathematics education] to make sense, but we should give it meaning [...] to develop a revolt, a rebellion, conceived as the stubbornness of doing something that is doomed to fail, of doing what is needed to do, or of doing what we are required to do in order to find/build meaning to our path." In this brief response paper, I aim to make use of my positionality as a member of the "global north," as well as my experience as an anarchist political activist in said global context (Bowers, 2021; Bowers & Lawler, 2021a, 2021b), in order to anticipate and subvert certain critiques and rhetorical evasions that I anticipate Parra's argument will prompt

Please cite as: Bowers, D. M. (2021). Urgency and the shameful escape of privilege: We move differently when we refuse to set aside the weight: A response to Aldo Parra. In D. Kolloosche (Ed.), *Exploring new ways to connect: Proceedings of the Eleventh International Mathematics Education and Society Conference* (Vol. 1, pp. 81–86). Tredition. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5469692>

among many members of that broadly privileged community (and particularly among members with multitudinous intersectional privileged identities). None of this should be taken as a critique of persons, but instead as a surfacing of the tacit ethical weight that privilege allows us to choose either to consciously bear or set aside in our choices of response. This is not simple iconoclasm, but instead an invitation to join us in a “hyper- and pessimistic activism,” (Foucault, 1983) an invitation to embrace “not the conviction that something will turn out well, but the certainty that something makes sense, regardless of how it turns out” (Havel, 1990, p. 181, as cited in Parra, 2021, in this volume).

To begin, I will briefly recapitulate the broad shape and sense of Parra’s plenary address (or, rather, the key thread that I am addressing in this paper), in order to help ensure we (writer/speaker and readers/listeners) begin from a place of some shared understanding, even if my sense of Parra’s words does not match your own. I will then outline some of the critiques and rhetorical evasions that I anticipate will comprise and confine the reactions of some, and especially many of those who have lived and been enculturated wholly or primarily into western neoliberal lines of thought (these lines of thought are also inextricably rooted in white supremacy, cis-hetero patriarchy, parochialism, abled supremacy, and so forth—these intransigent systems are part and parcel to western neoliberalism as surfaced in work such as Kendi, 2016). I will then respond to these anticipated reactions, not with an eye towards debunking or refuting per se, but instead with an eye towards consciously surfacing the ethical weight that they bypass or ignore. I conclude by restating and amplifying Parra’s call to action: Let us leverage our communal power to give mathematics education, a rebellion of doing what is needed and “good” regardless or in spite of whether such efforts are doomed to failure.

Recapitulation of Parra: Urgency and ethics

Parra’s text begins at the end, or rather an end: Apocalypse. Pandemic, postfactualism, and pareidolia, acting in concert, represent an existential threat, not just in the sense that the existence of many people/populations is literally threatened through violence (police brutality; Capitalists holding hostage water, housing, medical treatment, and other means of survival; etc.), but also in the insidious sense that the already distant possibility of a life (relatively) free of oppression is being crushed under the deleterious explosion of mounting exploitation, unemployment, inequality, deprivation, and so forth. We could add much more to this already horrifying list of existential threats, such as the accelerating climate catastrophe (IPCC, 2021) or the threat and risks associated with artificial intelligence, but even without expanding the list of threats it seems clear that there is an *ethical weight* tied to how we choose to respond (or not respond) to these threats, as well as an *urgency* to when we respond. It is also worth noting at this juncture that for many people, *apocalypse* is not a hypothetical future, but a reality of their present and past. “Dystopia” and “post-apocalypse” are common language used in privileged spaces to describe privileged people coming to experience what so many others across, for example, Indigenous and Black diasporic communities have already experienced (note that we could add to this list innumerable queer,

disabled/neurodivergent, and non-Christian communities). In other words, the ethical weight and urgency Parra describes already existed prior to the present moment, but the present moment has invited a growing group of people to consciously notice this weight and urgency.

From this apocalyptic beginning, Parra moves towards a more hopeful aspect of this line of inquiry: Extant resistance of omnipresent violence. Through a variety of examples, Parra discusses the potentially revolutionary power of redirecting our values and actions away from larger systems of oppression and towards something more local and communal. He describes examples of a vision of mathematics education that already exists in the margins, one rooted in resistance and emancipation. When the values of communities drive our work, when communities are able to determine the metrics of success, there is the potential to fundamentally change the nature of what we can accomplish. When communities are understood to include both human and non-human existences, a perspective which necessarily moves beyond viewing all symbolic and material assemblages as mere resources to be exploited, this revolutionary potential grows. Parra is careful to temper these claims with reference to work describing the innumerable ways oppressive systems capture and claim mechanisms intended as emancipatory (e.g., Cabral & Baldino, 2019; Pais, 2012). – Consider, for example, the way “strengths-based pedagogy” was/is intended to surface value in the margins of society, but is commonly enacted as “what can the center take from the margins to strengthen itself.” This *capture* happens when the values ultimately being served are still the values of the oppressive systems (well symbolized by the absurd trend of rainbow-colored hostile architecture; the queer are disproportionately rendered homeless, so painting an anti-homeless bench in Pride colors represents a grimly fascinating material representation of this *capture*), and the value in the margin is simply a resource. Parra ends with a challenge: One piece of power that we inarguably have is the power of self- and communal-definition. What mathematics education *is*, broadly speaking, does not make ethical sense. If we want it to make sense, we have to leverage our power to make it make sense. We may still be doomed to fail against the overwhelming Authoritarian force we face, but even without the conviction that our efforts will turn out well, we can at least have “the certainty that something makes sense, regardless of how it turns out” (Havel, 1990, p. 181, as cited in Parra, 2021, in this volume). We can know that we are *doing good* even if we are doomed to fail.

Rhetorical evasion: Anticipating and responding

Based in my experiences as an Anarchist activist in the cultural context of the United States, there are a variety of common forms of rhetorical evasion or pushback I anticipate Parra’s messaging prompting from the well-meaning privileged. I obviously can’t name or respond to these exhaustively, but given the *ethical weight* and *urgency* of Parra’s messaging, there are several that may warrant explicit naming and critical reflection. In particular, I will acknowledge and offer a reflective counter to these three responses, each of which have been extremely common roadblocks in efforts to organize with the intersectionally privileged: (1) I wish I could do more, but I can’t; (2) Reform is a better path than revolution; and (3) I can

both satisfy what the system, as it exists, demands of me, *and* oppose the self-same system. In each case, my goal is not to offer an exhaustive response, but instead to invite critical self-reflection/discussion and advance more emancipatory futurities in the context of the *ethical weight* and *urgency* surfaced by Parra.

“I wish I could do more, but I can’t...”

When I hear people voice this concern, what I actually hear them expressing is the tension they feel between their desire to *do good* and their anxiety or fear of the vulnerable position that *doing good* would ultimately demand of them. If you are white (as I am), then opposing white Supremacy ultimately demands that you let go of the safety net that privilege affords; if you are a cis-heterosexual man (as I am not), then opposing cis-hetero patriarchy demands that oppose the very ideologies and mechanisms that keep you safe; if you are neurotypical (as I am not), then opposing neurotypical supremacy demands that you let go of cultural norms that privilege your ways of being and thinking; etc. I do not blame you for feeling this tension. However, it is worth noting that this vulnerability that you can opt to ignore along your privileged identities is something that the marginalized can not opt out of. Thus, I ask: If you were to sit with this vulnerability, day in and day out, for days and months and years at a time, how would that affect your choices and the way you move through life?

“Reform is a better path than revolution...”

Is it possible to reform the system/institution to the point of emancipation without fundamentally changing it? If fundamental change is necessary, then what we are doing is revolution, and what you are distinguishing is a slow revolution from a faster one. When is it appropriate to allow a slow revolution? Certainly not in a moment of *urgency*. In contexts where your positionality is privileged, would you feel differently about how quickly we need change if you instead imagined yourself as one of the marginalized?

Consider police “reform.” If you are relatively safe around police (my whiteness offers some safety, but my queerness and neurodivergence still put me in a great deal of danger when engaging with police), maybe a slow revolution sounds fine. However, if you or your children are at risk of extrajudicial execution, perhaps that is less likely to seem like a reasonable option.

“I can both satisfy the system and oppose it...”

I conclude at the same place conversations such as these so often seem to culminate: “Both/And.” To be clear, it is not unreasonable to believe (or to advance the belief) that we can act in some ways at some times that empower the system, and in other ways at other times that oppose it – I certainly agree. However, “both/and” responses encounter an ethical problem when the two categories under consideration are not constructed as equal, as when one focus is more/less oppressive than the other. In such cases, this response advances equity only symbolically and not materially. In parallel to Dubbs’ (2020) observations regarding Sfar’s (1998) metaphors for learning, who diverges from the claim that “it is essential that

we try to live with both” (p. 8), this is a situation where it is uniquely trivial to observe that one focus can be said to be better than the other, with better being that which is more equitable. Uncritically suggesting that we can do “both/and” without a critical lens reifies oppression and marginalization, and it will continue to do so until such time as “We... normalize (and expect) the full taking up the philosophical and theoretical underpinnings of all of our work (even work that is not considered ‘philosophical’)” (Bakker, Cai, & Zenger, 2021, p. 12). In other words, if we do not consciously wrestle with the often tacit ways that our beliefs and consequent methods advance the interests of a violent system, we stand little chance of meaningfully opposing that violence. As it stands, “Both/And” is a product of late abled cis-hetero patriarchal white supremacist capitalism and neoliberalism, a signifier for the confrontation of postmodernity contra modernity, and as such it enables a disarmament of ideas that would otherwise be directed at critiquing late capitalism. In contrast to Hegelian synthesis, “Both/And” bypasses the negative moment of determination. Thus, “Both/And” isn’t really “Both/And...” it’s just an exercise in neoliberal thought (Bowers, 2021, p. 80).

Conclusion

I opened this paper with the words of Malcolm X, an evocative and deeply visceral attack on Centrism. That description of those words may sound strange to some who perceive Liberalism (e.g. the Democratic political party in the United States) as the “Left,” but Liberalism is not and has never been the Left – instead, it is only the leftmost arm of the establishment, the leftmost position tolerated by the entangled authoritarian systems we occupy. In a word, it is the *captured* left. To be clear, if you currently identify as a Liberal or a Democrat, I do not think you are cruel or unreasonable; instead, I think only that you are *human*. In this culture of internalized white supremacy, cis-hetero patriarchy, abled supremacy, and neoliberal Capitalism, I would be deeply surprised by any relatively privileged member of society who did not identify in this way at some point. However, just because it is reasonable and human to find yourself here at some point in your journey of rhizomatic growth does not mean that it is an adequate place to stop. The fear, frustration, and rage we hear in Malcolm’s words are real, and are not unique to him, nor unique to matters of race. The more marginalized the community I find myself learning with and from, the more likely I am to hear exactly Malcolm’s sentiments. Now, in these final moments, I leave you with one final synthesis statement, one final call to action: Be not satisfied with centrism or the status quo, and force yourself to sit with the tensions that you have the privileged capacity to escape. We move differently when we force ourselves to carry the weight of the violences that privilege allows us to ignore (Bowers, Forthcoming).

If you have come here to help me, you are wasting your time. But if you have come because your liberation is bound up with mine, then let us work together. (Lilla Watson in community with other Aboriginal Rights activists)

References

- Bakker, A., Cai, J., & Zenger, L. (2021). Future themes of mathematics education research: An international survey before and during the pandemic. *Educational Studies in Mathematics*, 107, 1–24.
- Bowers, D. M. (2021). Anarchist mathematics education: Ethic, motivation, and praxis [Doctoral dissertation, Michigan State University]. Proquest.
- Bowers, D. M. (forthcoming). Examples, exceptions, and monster barring: Unsettling centrism in mathematics education. *Journal for Theoretical & Marginal Mathematics Education*.
- Bowers, D. M., & Lawler, B. R. (2021a). Anarchism as a methodological foundation in mathematics education: A portrait of resistance. In D. Kollosche (Ed.), *Exploring new ways to connect: Proceedings of the Eleventh International Mathematics Education and Society Conference* (Vol. 1, pp. 86–330). Tredition. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5393560>
- Bowers, D. M. & Lawler, B. R. (2021b). Reconciling tensions in equity discourse through an anti-hierarchical (anarchist) theory of action. In A. I. Sacristán, J. C. Cortés-Zavala, & P. M. Ruiz-Arias (Eds.), *Mathematics education across cultures: Proceedings of the Forty-Second Meeting of the North American Chapter of the International Group for Psychology in Mathematics Education* (pp. 518–524). PME-NA.
- Cabral, T. C. B., & Baldino, R. R. (2019). The social turn and its big enemy: A leap forward. In J. Subramanian (Ed.), *Proceeding of the Tenth International Mathematics Education and Society Conference* (pp. 32–46). MES10.
- Dubbs, C. H. (2020). Learner, student, mathematician: What we call the subjects of mathematics education. *Philosophy of Mathematics Education*, 36.
- Foucault, M. (1983). On the genealogy of ethics: An overview of work in progress. In H. Dreyfus & P. Rabinow (Eds.), *Michel Foucault: Beyond structuralism and hermeneutics* (pp. 229–264). University of Chicago Press.
- Havel, V. (1990). *Disturbing the peace: A conversation with Karel Hvížďala*. Vintage.
- Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change. (2021). *Climate change 2021: The physical science basis. Contribution of Working Group I to the Sixth Assessment Report of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change*. Cambridge University Press.
- Kendi, I. X. (2016). *Stamped from the beginning: The definitive history of racist ideas in America*. Nation Books.
- Parra, A. (2021). Mathematics education, researchers and local communities: A critical encounter in times of pandemic, pareidolia and post-factualism. In D. Kollosche (Ed.), *Exploring new ways to connect: Proceedings of the Eleventh International Mathematics Education and Society Conference* (Vol. 1, pp. 86–80). Tredition. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5457124>
- Pais, A. (2012). A critical approach to equity. In O. Skovmose & B. Greer (Eds.), *Opening the cage: Critique and politics of mathematics education* (pp. 49–92). Sense.
- Sfard, A. (1998). On two metaphors for learning and the dangers of choosing just one. *Educational Researcher*, 27(2), 4–13.